

IMPACT ABSORPTION OF COMPOSITES WITH SHEAR THICKENING FLUID FILLED FOAMS

M. Soutrenon, V. Michaud*

Laboratoire de Technologie des Composites et Polymères, Ecole Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne, CH 1015 Lausanne, Switzerland

* Corresponding author (veronique.michaud@epfl.ch)

Keywords: *Impact, Shear thickening fluids, Energy dissipation*

1 Introduction

Composite structures are often sensitive to impact, leading to premature damage and failure, which is difficult to detect. Several strategies have been proposed to improve the composite resin toughness, or to introduce interlayers [1,2]. Another approach is to introduce impact protection on the surface. For low velocity impact, viscoelastic impact absorbers can be laid on the composite, and show good protection, provided that the layer has the proper combination of loss and stiffness properties [3-6]. The advantage of this approach is its non-intrusiveness and the preservation of the initial material properties, in particular in shear or bending, and the possibility to selectively protect critical areas, in particular for applications where inspection and repair are difficult to carry out, as in space.

A potential alternative material for impact absorbers are shear thickening fluids (STF), which are concentrated colloidal suspensions that undergo a large viscosity increase, up to 3 orders of magnitude at a critical shear rate and for a given level of stress. STF have been widely investigated in terms of their rheological properties [7,8, 9]. Shear thickening is a reversible phenomenon, and the transition from high to low viscosity after the end of a dynamic solicitation is instantaneous. The rise of viscosity between these two states, from a viscous liquid to that of a brittle solid is associated with large energy absorption attributed to the friction between clusters of particles forming hydroclusters, which increases during the transition [10]. This phenomenon can be used to dissipate energy from shocks or vibrations as it was demonstrated for dampers in automotive applications [11-14]. These materials, however, are liquid at rest, or form a weak physical gel, and are sensitive to their environment, as the carrier fluid, glycol, either evaporates or picks up humidity. In

consequence, these materials can find practical use only if they are properly encapsulated. Moreover, since they are activated by shear, the material form should be such that shear is promoted during service, as needed. For example, STF have been encapsulated in foams and tested in compression with various testing velocities, and the stiffening effect could be linked to the local behavior of the STF [15].

We report here on the processing of composite pads made of open cell foams, impregnated with a selected monodisperse colloidal suspension of silica in polyethylene glycol showing a shear thickening effect, which are then encapsulated in silicone. The efficiency of the manufactured pads is then tested for energy absorption upon impact, and compared to that of other energy absorption materials, such as rubber or silicone.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Materials

The shear thickening fluid (STF) was prepared with 500 nm diameter spherical silica particles from Nippon Shokubai Co. under reference name KE-P50. Polyethylene Glycol with an average molecular weight of 200 g.mol⁻¹ (PEG200) was purchased from VWR. The silicone used for encapsulation was a flexible (shore hardness 18) polycondensated silicone from Bluestar Silicones (RHODORSIL RTV-3318). The catalyst was the standard cata-24h with 5 parts of catalyst per 100 parts of RTV-3318. This silicone was also used in bulk as a comparison material. The foam was a flexible open-cell melamine resin foam (BASF, BASOTECH G or BASOTECH UL). The density of the foam was 9 kg/m³ for G and 6 kg/m³ for UL and the average pore size 150 μm.

Smactane® SP, a viscoelastic rubber material developed by SMAC for space applications, was also used for comparison.

2.2 Sample production method

STF was produced according to standard methods [12,16], with a volume fraction of 67.5 wt% of particles, which lead to a large shear thickening effect upon increasing shear strain. Fig.1 shows the typical behavior of the STF in flow rheology, with a critical shear rate of about 2-3/s when the suspension is well dispersed [16]. This fluid was infiltrated under vacuum at 70°C into cylindrical foam elements, 25 mm in diameter and 10 mm thick, placed in a mould. These foam elements were covered with silicone on the top and bottom part prior to infiltration, in order to provide a good adhesion between the foam and the silicone. The foam thus provided a three-dimensional scaffold to the STF and increased the local shear strain on the fluid. After infiltration was complete, the STF/foam composite was cooled down, and the sides encapsulated into silicone, to complete the sample encapsulation. It was demonstrated in earlier work [16] that the encapsulation of STF samples in silicone allowed the conservation of the rheological properties over time, limiting all issues of degassing or humidity intake.

Samples of foam infiltrated with the carrier fluid PEG only were produced under vacuum infusion at room temperature, and bulk samples of Smactane and of Silicone with the same size as the foams were also produced for comparison.

2.3 Compression testing

Compression tests were carried out on cylindrical samples similar to the ones for impact tests using a UTS TestSysteme (Germany), with a 50 or 1000 N load cell and a constant displacement rate of 0.002 mm/min, corresponding to a deformation rate $d\epsilon/dt=3 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ s}^{-1}$.

2.4 Measurement of viscoelastic properties

The viscoelastic properties of the materials used in this study, ie: STF, Smactane and Silicone were measured using a Rheometer (AR2000ex from TA instruments), at room temperature in shear mode. The tests were carried out in a room with controlled temperature at $23^{\circ}\text{C}\pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$. Parallel plates of 25mm diameter were used. Gaps were 800 μm for the STF,

2mm for Smactane and 1mm for the silicone. The plate surfaces were covered with sandpaper P220 (grain size of 68 μm) glued with cyanoacrylate glue as recommended in the literature. The tests consisted in an oscillatory stress ramp from 0.1 to 60000 Pa applied to the sample. They were conducted at four different frequencies for each sample: 0.1, 0.5, 1 and 2 Hz.

2.5 Impact testing

Impact tests were carried out using a free fall impact tower. The impact head was an aluminum cylinder with a diameter of 40 mm and a thickness of 20 mm to submit the samples to a homogeneous compression. The total carriage weight was 2.55 kg. A load cell mounted between the impact head and the carriage was used to measure the force during impact. The load cell, Kistler 9031a, was able to record forces up to 60 kN. The acquisition rate was set to 100 kHz. Two accelerometers, one on the carriage and one 5 cm away from the sample were used to measure the transmitted acceleration. The deformation of the samples was evaluated from high-speed video taken at 4000 fps with a Photron Fastcam Ultima APX. A schematic diagram of the impact tower is given in Fig. 2.

Analysis of the tests was as follows: the impact speed was kept to $V=3.92\text{m/s}$, corresponding to an energy of 5J. The Coefficient of Restitution COR was calculated as the square root of the ratio of the height after rebound (measured from the high-speed videos) over the drop height. Displacement was measured from the high-speed videos, using a matlab routine that follows the movement of the edges of the samples.

3 Results and discussion

Five types of samples were tested: FoamG/STF, FoamUL/STF, Foam/PEG only, pure silicone, and Smactane.

3.1 Compression moduli

First, the compression modulus of these materials was measured with static simple compression tests, and the results are given in Fig. 3 and Table 1. The moduli were taken as the slope of the curve between 0 and 30% deformation. Clearly, Smactane has the highest static modulus and follows a linear behavior in the range investigated. The silicone is known to exhibit a two-stage hyper elastic behavior with an

initial low modulus followed by a higher modulus region after about 50% strain [17]; this non-linear behavior is observed here as well, as the slope starts to increase progressively.

The foam samples all showed a very low modulus. The foam alone was tested, and gave a modulus of 42 kPa. The Poisson ratio was visually observed to be 0, as previously reported for this material [18]. The foam was then tested with the STF inside, but before encapsulation. Considering the deformation rate imposed during the compression test, the local shear rate in a cell of 150 μ m of the foam can be approximated as the displacement velocity over the cell size, leading to about $2 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$, which is well below the critical shear rate for the STF used in this work, about 3 s^{-1} . As a result, the STF flows without thickening out of the sides of the foam cylinder, and exerts a very minor influence on the foam compressive behavior. A slight decrease was observed, most probably due to a destruction of some struts of the foam during infiltration. Nonetheless, the properties remained similar. Results follow the same trend for the STF/Foam UL system, with lower modulus values since the foam has a lower density. Finally, the STF/foam after encapsulation in silicone shows a slightly higher compression modulus, resulting from the presence of the sidewalls in silicone.

3.2 Viscoelastic properties

Table 2 reports the values of G' , G'' and $\text{tg}\delta$ at 2Hz, just above the critical shear rate for the pure STF, and at a stress amplitude of 100Pa for the silicone and the rubber materials. Silicone and Smactane are solids, Silicone has a rather low $\text{tg}\delta$ about 0.04, whereas Smactane's is one order of magnitude greater, around 0.37. Master curves describing the overall behavior of the materials over a range of temperatures or frequencies could not be established in the frame of this work, however, Fig. 4 shows the Master curve for $\text{tg}\delta$, from the Smactane datasheet, showing an increase with frequency at room temperature, up to 1.1 around 400Hz.

STF exhibits a very different behavior; it is a liquid suspension that tends to form a physical gel at rest, with a modulus in the 500Pa range, which increases to about 2kPa after the transition. During transition, $\text{tg}\delta$ goes through a maximum around 2 to 3,

indicating a large amount of dissipated energy, and the storage and loss moduli drop before increasing steadily after the transition, as shown in Fig. 5. This behavior was not tested at frequencies above 2Hz, but is expected to remain similar at higher frequencies.

3.3 Impact testing results

Impact testing was performed under 5 Joules of impact energy for all samples. Fig. 6 shows extracts from the videos for the STF/Foam G sample and Smactane. The STF/foam samples did not lead to any major rebound, compared to Smactane or to the Silicone samples. PEG/Foam samples were destroyed by the impact and so their behavior could not be reported. Maximum strain recorded varied between 55 and 70% during impact; no residual deformation was observed after impact for the 4 types of samples.

The force during impact versus time is reported on Fig. 7. STF/Foam samples are shown to lead to the lowest force, followed by Smactane and by the Silicone. For an elastic material, the maximal force during impact, F_{max} is expected to be:

$F_{\text{max}} = E \cdot S \cdot \epsilon_m$ where E is the Elastic modulus of the material, S the surface and ϵ_m the maximal strain [3], which leads to severely underestimated forces (by up to one order of magnitude), so it is clear that a viscoelastic approach needs to be taken to interpret the results.

Fig. 8 plots the displacement versus time for the materials during the first impact. For all samples, the compression speed is approximated as $u = 6\text{mm}/0.004\text{s} = 1.5 \text{ m/s}$, which corresponds to a deformation rate $d\epsilon/dt = 150 \text{ s}^{-1}$. With this rate, assuming that the Poisson ratio of the Basotect foam is nil, the shear rate inside a foam cell during impact corresponds to $d\gamma/dt = u/\text{cellsize} = 10^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$. This is far above the critical shear rate for the STF used in this study (which is close to 3 s^{-1}), so the STF shear thickened during impact, and as a result, the force increased quite rapidly as observed on Fig. 7.

Force versus displacement curves are given in Fig. 9. This curve was obtained by synchronizing the force response with the displacement measured in the high-speed videos. All curves are hysteretic, displaying energy absorption as expected, with the minimal dissipated energy observed for the most elastic material, the silicone. The behavior observed

for Smactane follows what is expected for a rubber material, as shown by Chen and Lakes [3] or Goyal et al. [6]. The silicone clearly shows the two-stage behavior of the compression modulus, first deforming greatly with little force increase, and then exerting a large resistance to impact, and showing a peak force up to 3kN. Calculation of F_{max} according to Chen for a viscoelastic material is as follows:

$$F_{max} = \frac{mV^2}{U_{max}} \exp(-tg[(\delta/2)(\pi - 2\delta)]) \quad (1)$$

which gives values of respectively 770N for RTV-3318 and 658N for Smactane, if we take the $tg\delta$ values as indicated in the table. It is still somewhat under evaluated compared to the actual results.

The STF/foam samples display a slightly different behavior: in the initial stages of deformation, the modulus is very low and almost no force arises. Then, the STF starts to stiffen and a higher force is observed, that remains constant with time as the STF flows within the foam towards the sides. At the maximum displacement, the force sharply drops to zero, and the rebound of the sample is with almost no force. Use of Foam G or UL shows a small difference only in the behavior, as it is dominated by the STF. In both cases, a large amount of energy is dissipated.

The coefficient of restitution (COR) was calculated for the samples, and the values are given in Fig. 10 for Smactane, STF/foam G and UL. The coefficient could not be measured in our set-up for the silicone, as the rebound was high, and out of the frame of the video camera. It was nonetheless estimated with the time of flight, to be 0.86. STF shows the lowest COR, indicating the best energy dissipation from these samples, up to 85%. Successive impacts showed a good reproducibility of the behavior up to 5 impacts, with some degradation of the foam properties, in particular for the low-density foam.

Using the analysis of Chen and Lakes, a correlation should be found between the COR and $tg\delta$ of the material, for a viscoelastic material as follows:

$$COR = \sqrt{\frac{H_1}{H_0}} = \sqrt{(\cos \delta + tg(\delta/2) \sin \delta) \exp(-2tg(\delta/2)(\pi - \delta))} \quad (2)$$

Fig. 11 plots this relation, together with the value of COR found for the materials of this study. The

corresponding $tg\delta$ values are all higher than measured for the 2Hz case, as expected, and correspond quite well for the Smactane case to the expected value at this deformation rate. For the STF, the corresponding value is very high, in any case we do not expect the analytical model of Eq. 2 to be valid for STF, since energy absorption is through a different mechanism.

Finally, the acceleration was recorded on the impact head, and on the table near the sample, as shown in Fig. 12. The lowest transmitted acceleration was found for the STF/Foam or PEG/Foam samples, compared to the Smactane, for example, by using the dissipating effect of the fluid phase. The STF/Foam pads are thus shown to be efficient in impact protection, as well as in protecting other parts of the structure close to the pad.

4 Conclusions

Compared to a more traditional rubber layer, STF/foam composites show very large energy absorption, up to 85%, that can be repeated through several impacts. In parallel, smaller accelerations are transmitted from the impact. These pads could thus find application to protect composite structures. In parallel, since STF cannot be used in practical structures, since they are liquid, we proposed a method to insert the STF into a foam scaffold and encapsulate the assembly into a silicone layer. The silicone encapsulation ensures that the suspension does not evaporate or gain humidity during service, and furthermore, is shown to generate low outgassing in space applications. Further tests should be conducted to quantify the protection of composite structures with these materials, as well as to improve the mechanical properties of the scaffolding foam, to reach the best compromise between mechanical integrity over time, and large deformations.

Fig. 1: Flow viscosity of the STF used in this study

Fig. 3: Static compression curves for (a) Smactane, (b) Silicone, (c) encapsulated STF/FoamG, (d) STF/Foam G not encapsulated.

Fig.2: Schematic diagram of the impact tower

Table 1: Compression modulus of the encapsulated STF/FoamG, non encapsulated STF/Foam G, FoamG alone, STF/foam UL not encapsulated, Foam UL alone, Silicone and Smactane.

Material	Compression modulus (MPa)
Encapsulated STF/Foam G	0.21
STF/Foam G not encapsulated	0.031
Foam G	0.042
STF/Foam UL not encapsulated	0.010
Foam UL	0.016
RTV-3318	0.26
Smactane	1.52

Table 2: Dynamic properties of the materials investigated, at 2Hz

Material	G'(Pa)	G''(Pa)	tgδ
STF	43±5	134±17	3.2
RTV-3318	69 10 ³ ± 4 10 ³	2.810 ³ ±0.510 ³	0.04
Smactane	6.8 10 ⁵	2.8 10 ⁵	0.37

Fig. 4: Tgδ as a function of reduced frequency for Smactane at 20°C.

Fig.5: Storage modulus G', Loss modulus G'' and tgδ as a function of the stress amplitude, for the STF alone in oscillatory shear at 2Hz.

Fig. 6: STF/Foam G (above) and Smactane (below) during impact testing, left, just before impact, middle, at the maximum deformation, and right, just after rebound.

Fig 9: Force versus displacement curve for the first rebound of a 5J impact

Fig 7: Force versus time for first rebound during a 5J impact

Fig 10: coefficient of restitution for first rebound of Smactane, encapsulated STF/foam G and UL during a 5J impact. The STF/Foam samples were tested successively 5 times.

Fig. 8: Displacement versus time during the first rebound during a 5J impact

Fig 11: COR versus $tg\delta$, calculated from Eq.(2)

Fig 12: Transmitted acceleration during impact

Acknowledgements

This work is funded by the European Space Agency under the Networking/Partnering Initiative program. G. Ladurée from ESTEC is thanked for help with data treatment and advice, and we thank N. Borhani and S. Khodaparast from the LTCM at EPFL for lending the high-speed camera and for their assistance.

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